

**THE HIPPOCAMPUS RECONSIDERED: GATED INFORMATIONAL TRANSFER ALLOWS
FORMATION OF COGNITIVE MAPS**

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Abstract: A hypothesis is offered for the functional role of the mammalian hippocampus in the ontogenetic formation of cognitive maps. We propose that the hippocampus functions as a GATE for the TRANSFER of sensory INFORMATION which when associated with each other allows the buildup of cognitive maps. These maps then are used by the animal for many types of exploratory behavior.

Introduction: Neonatal rabbits exhibit changes in exploratory behavior at the time of eye opening

Neonatal rabbits, like many mammals, are born with their eyes closed. In this helpless state, the newborn rabbit is totally dependent upon its mother for all of its needs and is developmentally programmed to stay close to the mother for a variety of reasons all of which are critical to the animal's survival (eg. avoiding predation, staying close to the source of food). Neonatal rabbits open their eyes around post-natal day 10 (P10) and almost immediately their behavior shifts from the earlier sedentary pattern to an exploratory mode in which they move about their immediate environment in a behavioral pattern than many investigators of the hippocampus have termed "spatial" or "cognitive mapping." The behavioral switch is a common behavioral feature of nearly all individuals of the species and probably serves a similar survival-enhancing function as the earlier neonatal behavior pattern in that cognitive mapping probably helps to avoid predation and other threats to the individual as soon as the hardware (ie the visual system) is in place to produce the raw data for the map. The character of these behavioral changes suggested to us that it might be fruitful to investigate parameters of the neonatal rabbit hippocampus that had previously been shown to undergo changes both in classical conditioning of the adult rabbit nictitating membrane and in spatial "mapping" tasks in adult rat (namely the intrinsic electrophysiology of CA1 pyramidal cells and the distribution of membrane-associated protein kinase C). We have recently reported large parallel changes in the accommodation of CA1 neurons to current injection and the distribution of protein kinase C which occur around the time that the neonate opens its eyes (NEO, Sanchez-Andres and Olds, 1991). In the present paper, we argue that 1) such changes reflect the developmentally programmed engagement of the hippocampal mapping system, 2) that visual information has a special "privileged" access to

such a system, and 3) that the engagement of this system is one of the definitive events of early mammalian development in that it allows the newborn to create cognitive maps of its immediate environs.

Accommodation of CA1 neurons: Functional Disconnection of the Hippocampus

CA1 pyramidal cells from adult animals respond to current injection typically with a burst of action potentials which are superimposed on a depolarizing envelope. In the neonatal animal (prior to P10), this pattern of bursting, is not present. Instead, the neonate CA1 cells demonstrate an electrophysiological phenomenon of accommodation in which the neuron only fires a single (or several) action potentials in response to the same current injection. As the developmental program of the rabbit neonate progresses past NEO, this accommodation is rapidly replaced by the adult pattern of bursting. This normal pattern of development can be perturbed by occluding the eyes of the neonate prior to P10. In the case of neonates with occluded eyes, the CA1 cells seem to stay "arrested" in their accommodated state for at least several days after the normal transformation to the adult pattern. We hypothesize here that the net effect of the accommodation is to block functional transfer of information along the trisynaptic circuit of the hippocampus. This electrophysiological block is removed at precisely the same time that it becomes useful for the animal to show exploratory or spatial behaviors. We hypothesize that this block or gating subserves two important developmental purposes. First, it functionally disconnects the hippocampus. Many studies over the last forty years have indicated that functionally disconnecting the hippocampus results in deficits in exploratory or mapping behavior (Olton et al. 1978). O'Keefe and Nadel (1976) have gone so far as to suggest that the purpose of the hippocampus may in fact be to allow an animal to create cognitive maps. We suggest that functionally disconnecting the hippocampus may in fact prevent the animal from engaging in such exploratory behaviors at a time when those behaviors would be maladaptive. The second possible developmental purpose of the gating may be to allow normal neocortical development to be completed. Along analogous lines of thought, many investigators have hypothesized that geniculo-cortical afferent input allows competitive interaction in the dendritic arborizations of pyramidal cells in visual cortex which create the ocular dominance columns. Such normal neocortical development in the visual system then requires an activity dependent sequence of interactions between the sub-cortical afferents and the genetically-specified development of the neocortical cells themselves. Similarly, neocortical areas that are functionally afferent to the hippocampus (such as cingulate and entorhinal cortex) may require a sequence of such interactions for their normal development. Thus, it may be important to restrict hippocampal "outflow" at certain times during the developmental program. If as Teyler has suggested (Teyler and DiScenna, 1985), the hippocampus serves to index functional connections between associated cortical modules, then it would be perhaps important to prevent such indexing at some period in development when such modules may "not be ready" for associations to be formed.

Hippocampal PKC in rabbit neonates

Protein kinase C (PKC) is a calcium-lipid dependent protein kinase (an enzyme which catalyzes the phosphorylation of specific substrate proteins) first characterized by Nishizuka in

1979. It has since been found to play a ubiquitous role in regulating cellular function in most eukaryotic systems (Nishizuka 1988) and unlike most kinases, is characterized by requiring both an appropriate lipid milieu and a Calcium signal for physiological activation.

In the neonatal rabbit, membrane-associated PKC shows a unique distribution within the CA1 cell field that parallels the accommodation of the CA1 pyramidal cells. Intense bands of increased membrane-associated PKC can be seen on either side of the cell body layer (stratum pyramidale). This pattern of distribution has to our knowledge, never been previously described. In the immediate period during and after NEO, the pattern of hippocampal membrane-associated PKC shifts to one characterized by heavy specific binding of the label within both the stratum pyramidale and the stratum oriens. This change however, lasts only for several days after NEO and seems to become more diffuse as development progresses.

Protein Kinase C and Learning

Recently, PKC has been found to play an important role in rabbit and rat associative learning (For review: see Olds and Alkon, 1991) as assessed by quantitative autoradiographic techniques. Other methodologies have tended to confirm the evolving hypothesis that PKC activation may serve as a nexus in the chain of neuronal events that leads to the laying down and storage of memory.

Learning-specific changes in ionic currents in CA1 pyramidal cells parallel changes in hippocampal PKC

The changes in PKC may be related to the accommodation changes since it has been clearly shown in several laboratories that activation of PKC with phorbol esters inactivates potassium channels in hippocampal CA1 cells. Such micromolecular channel changes are likely candidates for subserving the observed "macro" changes in accommodation. Additionally, adult rabbits that have undergone classical conditioning of their nictitating membrane also show long term decreases in the calcium-dependent potassium current of the CA1 pyramidal cells which underlie a learning-specific decrease in the After Hyperpolarization date (Sanchez-Andres and Alkon). These electrophysiological changes with classical conditioning in the adult rabbit therefore also parallel changes in the distribution of membrane-associated PKC and may share related characteristics with the developmental changes described in the previous section.

Sensory access to the Hippocampus during development:

The visual system may be critical to the formation of cognitive maps (O'Keefe and Nadel) and therefore its privileged access to the hippocampal formation may be a *sine qua non* for normal development of "hippocampal" behaviors. Certainly this reasoning would be parsimonious with the short term occluded eye data regarding CA1 cell accommodation. However, we believe that the longer term accommodation data (where the pattern eventually returns to its normal developmental course) might be explained by other sensory modalities that

gain alternative access to the hippocampus. For example, it is clear from a number of studies that both the auditory and olfactory systems follow roughly similar courses of development in the neonatal rabbit. Consequently, it is not surprising that after a period of "adaptation" to visual deprivation, the hippocampus may go on to form alternative cognitive maps based on auditory or olfactory cues (as these sensory modalities develop and come on-line). The access of these sensory modalities to the hippocampus could in turn lead to an abolition of the neonate pattern of accommodation in the CA1 cells. With the hippocampus now functioning in "exploratory mode", cognitive maps, albeit more primitive ones, could be formed.

GITH: Gated Information Transfer Hypothesis

The above arguments lead us to propose the following hypothesis for hippocampal involvement in neurodevelopment. We call it GITH (Gated Informational Transfer Hypothesis), because we feel that the hippocampus acts as a gate for the transfer of sensory information of various types to archicortical and/or neocortical processing loci that lead to the formation of cognitive maps. An assumption of the hypothesis is that cognitive maps are made early in development and are used for the progressive evolution of exploratory behaviors that allow the animal to "make sense" of its environment. Under normal (non-pathological) conditions, these maps are built up in a manner dependent upon an interaction between the visual system and the hippocampus. While this visual-hippocampal interaction is required for normal development, it is not absolutely necessary for the formation of cognitive maps. In the absence of the visual modality, alternative modalities can be employed by the animal to build up such informational structures (albeit in a delayed fashion).

There are two important aspects of this hypothesis which are important to note. The first is that the hippocampus enables the creation of the maps. It is not necessarily the locus. Thus, the hippocampal system can be "engaged" to allow map formation, or "dis-engaged" at a time in development when such map formation is counter-productive to the animal's overall fitness.

The second aspect of the hypothesis deals with the issue of the role of sensory information input to the "engagement" of the hippocampal mapping system. In our formulation of GITH, sensory input to the hippocampal formation is absolutely necessary to the engagement of the system to allow map formation. Such afferent information by no means has to be mono-synaptic. In the case of the olfactory system the input is obviously much more direct than in the case of the visual system, though there is ample evidence for hippocampal access in both cases. We propose here that the associations of such sensory informational packets are the business of the hippocampus and that such associations allow the buildup of cognitive maps for the animal. This is a testable aspect of the model since presumably by isolating the hippocampus from all sensory modalities, it might be possible to not only prevent cognitive map formation, but also to prevent the development of accommodational changes in CA1 neurons and/or PKC distributional changes.

Finally, we attempt to consider the striking phenomenon of hippocampal place cells (O'Keefe and Dostrovsky, 1971) within the framework of GITH. Certainly, it does seem that since the place cells are to some extent the nearest thing we have to a measured manifestation of

"cognitive maps". It is therefore likely that their developmental profile should be qualitatively similar to the accommodation and PKC distribution results already mentioned. Secondly, the "receptive" fields of such cells should be alterable by eye occlusion experiments in a similar manner to the accommodation data. This putative sensitivity of the place cells is suggested by the work of Muller and Kubie (1987) where the receptive field of the place cell was found to be under the control of a single visual cue. But above all, we believe that the place cell phenomenology is merely a reflection of the underlying informational transfer. The place cells develop their receptive fields because they are involved in the gated informational transfer of spatially relevant sensory information in much the same way that simple and complex cells of the primary visual cortex develop their receptive fields as a byproduct of their function in extracting features from the visual world.

Essentially, we are proposing that one function of the hippocampus is to gate the processing of information necessary to the formation of cognitive maps. The formation of such maps is dependent upon both an intact hippocampus and the integrity of the information itself. In some cases (as in early development for the rabbit) where the formation of cognitive maps (and the concomitant development of exploratory behaviors) is counter to the individual's survival, the hippocampal gate is shut down. When the raw information that the hippocampus "needs" to allow the formation of maps becomes available, then the gate is opened and the normal repertoire of exploratory behaviors goes forward. In conclusion, GITH provides a framework for understanding a variety of neurobiological data gleaned from observing the hippocampus in development. We believe that it is useful because it offers a number up a number of predictions which can be tested in the laboratory.

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